

Pulse schemes for detection of quaternary carbons with and without proton decoupling[†]

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Four new pulse sequences are proposed for the detection of quaternary carbons. The primary, secondary and tertiary (CH₃, CH₂ and CH) carbons are suppressed by creating their multiple quantum coherences, which are dephased by the pulsed field gradients in these schemes. Two of the schemes incorporate proton decoupling during acquisition resulting in the enhanced sensitivity of detection. The other two schemes, which do not involve the proton decoupling during acquisition, enable the observation of the long-range carbon-proton couplings, if any. Description of the pulse schemes is provided and the experiments are demonstrated on three samples, a hexapeptide [(CH₃)₃C-O-CO-Val-Val-Val-Aib-Val-Aib-OCH₃, where Aib is methyl-alanyl residue], cholesterol acetate and friedelan-7-one.

Spectral editing methods, particularly for ¹³C NMR form a very important tool in spectral assignments. They have undergone a lot of evolution with time leading to techniques that are quicker and simpler to perform. While the multidimensional NMR methods are essential for complex systems with large number of interacting nuclei, the use of one-dimensional experiments continues to be important for relatively small molecules for quick and routine analyses of the ¹³C NMR spectra¹⁻¹⁶. In an earlier communication, a new pulse technique for the detection of quaternary carbons was described¹⁷. The suppression of protonated carbons, in this technique, depends on proton decoupling during acquisition in addition to application of pulsed field gradients. The application of decoupling power has advantages as well as disadvantages. The advantage is that it enhances the sensitivity and resolution. However, by the decoupling during acquisition, the information on the long-range proton-carbon couplings is lost. In addition, the use of decoupling power may alter the sample temperature resulting in the possible changes in the sample or spectral parameters. It would therefore be ideal to have a set of experiments, which provides the flexibility in terms of whether to use the decoupling or not. The pulse schemes presented herein achieve this objective. The experiments are demonstrated to show that the application of decoupling

power is optional for obtaining information on the quaternary carbons.

Results and discussion

The proposed pulse techniques are shown in Fig. 1. The sequences differ in the presence or absence of saturation of protons during relaxation and/or decoupling during acquisition. In all these schemes CH₃, CH₂ and CH carbons are suppressed efficiently by creating their multiple quantum coherences and then dephasing them using pulsed field gradients. The quaternary carbons pass through unaffected.

Fig. 1a involves saturation of protons during relaxation and decoupling during acquisition and hence it provides quaternary carbon spectrum with maximum sensitivity due to NOE during relaxation and decoupling during acquisition. This sequence serves as an alternative to that described earlier¹⁷ for quaternary carbon detection. Fig. 1b is an inverse gated decoupled sequence for obtaining quaternary carbons. This is same as scheme 1a except the absence of saturation of protons during relaxation. Hence this sequence provides quaternary carbon signals without NOE and is, therefore, useful for quantitative estimation. Fig. 1c is same as 1a except that there is no saturation of protons during relaxation and no decoupling during acquisition. This sequence, due to the absence of decoupling during acquisition provides

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information on the long-range proton-carbon couplings in addition to detecting quaternary signals. However, the absence of saturation of protons during relaxation reduces sensitivity because of the absence of NOE. Pulse scheme 1d is same as the sequence 1a except that the decoupling of protons is absent during acquisition and hence it also provides quaternary carbons with long-range proton-carbon couplings like the scheme 1c. The advantage of this sequence over 1c is the gain in sensitivity by NOE due to the saturation of protons during relaxation.

Detection of quaternary carbons in the earlier scheme¹⁷ is based on decoupling during acquisition to suppress the signals coming from CH₂ carbons while suppressing other protonated carbons by dephasing using pulsed field gradients. We show in this paper that it is also possible to suppress the protonated carbons without using proton decoupling. The pulse schemes presented in Fig. 1 are similar to the earlier scheme¹⁷ with a major difference of a proton 90° pulse at the end of the 2τ period. The evolution of the magnetization in Fig. 1a for C, CH, CH₂ and CH₃ carbons is briefly explained below by the product operator formalism¹⁸. *I* and *S* refer to ¹H and ¹³C spins, respectively. Since all the four sequences of Fig. 1 are similar, the explanation for Fig. 1a is applicable to others as well. The phases of all the pulses are kept constant along *x*. Gradient pulse pair *g*₁ : *g*₁ is used to remove the artifacts that might arise due to 180° pulse imperfections and the gradient pulse *g*₂ is used for dephasing the multiple quantum coherences involving all the protonated carbons.

For quaternary carbons, the first 90° carbon pulse creates transverse magnetization ($-I_y$). At the end of the delay period, 2τ, an echo is formed. This transverse magnetization is converted into *S*_z magnetization by the second carbon 90° pulse which does not get affected due to the proton 90° pulse and the dephasing gradient pulse, *g*₂. Finally, the last 90° carbon pulse converts the *z*-magnetization into observable transverse magnetization.

For CH carbons, the first 90° carbon pulse creates transverse carbon magnetization which evolves for a period 2τ under the influence of the one bond coupling to proton. When the delay 2τ is set 1/2*J*_{CH}, antiphase magnetization (2*I*_z*S*_x) is created. This antiphase magnetization gets converted into multiple quantum coherences ($-2I_yS_x$) by the subsequent carbon and proton 90° pulses. The gradient pulse *g*₂ dephases these coherences, and thus the signals from CH carbons are suppressed.

For CH₂ carbons, the carbon transverse magnetization created after the first carbon 90° pulse evolves under the influence of the coupling to two directly attached protons

Fig. 1. Pulse schemes for quaternary carbons detection. Thin and thick filled bars represent 90° and 180° pulses, respectively. The default phase for the pulses is *x*. Gradient pulse pair *g*₁ : *g*₁ remove the artifacts caused by the imperfect 180° pulses and gradient *g*₂ is used for dephasing multiple quantum coherences involving protonated carbons. The duration and strength of the gradients used are *g*₁ = (1.0 ms, 5 G/cm); *g*₂ = (1.5 ms, 10 G/cm). (a) Pulse scheme for providing quaternary carbons with saturation of protons during relaxation and proton decoupling during acquisition; (b) pulse scheme with no saturation of protons during relaxation, for obtaining quaternary carbons for quantitative estimation; (c) pulse scheme for quaternary carbon detection with long-range proton couplings. Note that there is no saturation of protons during relaxation and no decoupling during acquisition either, in this scheme; (d) pulse sequence for obtaining quaternary carbons with long-range proton couplings and enhanced sensitivity due to NOE by saturation of protons during relaxation.

during the delay period, 2τ. At the end of the evolution for a period of 2τ = 1/2*J*_{CH}, doubly antiphase magnetization ($-4I_{1z}I_{2z}S_y$) is created. This magnetization gets converted into multiple quantum coherences ($-4I_{1y}I_{2y}S_z$) by the subsequent carbon and proton 90° pulses. The gradient pulse, *g*₂, dephases these coherences and thus the signals arising from CH₂ are suppressed in this sequence. It may be noted in the earlier scheme that CH₂ carbons get converted

into observable doubly antiphase transverse carbon magnetization. Therefore, it was required to switch on the decoupler to render this antiphase magnetization unobservable¹⁷.

Similarly, for CH₃ carbons, it can be seen that triply antiphase magnetization of carbon ($8I_{1z}I_{2z}I_{3z}S_x$) is created at the end of the delay $2\tau = 1/2J_{CH}$, due to the coupling of carbon to the three protons, which gets converted into multiple quantum coherences ($-8I_{1y}I_{2y}I_{3y}S_x$) by the subsequent carbon and proton 90° pulses. The gradient pulse g_2 dephases multiple quantum terms and hence the CH₃ carbons also become unobservable by this experiment.

Thus, in all the pulse schemes of Fig. 1, protonated carbons are suppressed completely while retaining only quaternary carbons. It is also clear from the schemes that application of proton decoupling during acquisition is optional. Introduction of proton decoupling during acquisition enables quaternary carbon detection with higher sensitivity and resolution due to narrow signals (Fig. 1a and 1b). While, in the absence of proton decoupling during acquisition, it is possible to observe long-range proton-carbon couplings, if any (Fig. 1c and 1d).

Figs. 2–4 show the ¹³C spectra of the peptide, cholesteryl acetate and friedelan-7-one, respectively, in CDCl₃ solvent. For the peptide, the region of the carbonyl carbons is also shown (Fig. 2). The structures of all the compounds are shown on top of the respective Figures. Quaternary carbons observed in the region 5–85 ppm are marked with asterisks in the structures. Spectra shown in (a) are the normal proton decoupled ¹³C spectra, while those in (b) are from the SEFT sequence showing positive signals for quaternary and CH₂ carbons, and negative signals for CH and CH₃ carbons (there are no CH₂ carbons in the hexapeptide, Fig. 2). Spectra shown in (c) are obtained from the pulse scheme described earlier¹⁷, which are shown here for comparison. The spectra (d) to (g) were obtained from the pulse schemes shown in Fig. 1a to 1d, respectively. The 2τ delay was set to 3.7, 4.2 and 4.2 ms for peptide, cholesteryl acetate and friedelan-7-one, respectively.

It is clearly seen from the spectra obtained from the new pulse schemes (spectra d to g in Figs. 2–4) that the protonated carbons are completely suppressed retaining only quaternary carbons. It is further seen from the spectra that the pulse schemes of Fig. 1a and 1b provide sharp signals (spectra d and e) due to proton decoupling during acquisition, similar to the spectra (c) obtained from the earlier scheme¹⁷. Pulse scheme 1b, due to the absence of saturation of protons during relaxation delay, can be used for quantitative estimation of the quaternary carbon signals when recorded

Fig. 2. ¹³C spectra in CDCl₃ solvent of 20 mmol⁻¹ hexapeptide with its structure shown at the top of the figure. (a) Normal proton decoupled ¹³C spectrum; (b) SEFT spectrum showing positive signals for quaternary carbons and negative signals for CH and CH₃ carbons; (c) spectrum obtained using the pulse sequence of the earlier report (17); (d) spectrum obtained from pulse scheme Fig. 1a; (e) spectrum obtained from pulse scheme of Fig. 1b for quantitative estimation; (f) spectrum obtained from pulse scheme of Fig. 1c (Note the lines are broad due to long-range proton couplings); (g) spectrum obtained from pulse scheme of Fig. 1d. Here the lines are broad due to long-range proton couplings, however, the intensities are much higher when compared to the signals in (f) due to the enhancement of the signals by NOE during relaxation.

with sufficiently long relaxation delay.

As expected, the quaternary carbon signals in the spectra (f) and (g) are broad due to the large number of long-range proton-carbon couplings. It is possible to observe well resolved multiplet structure for quaternary carbons from the systems with fewer number of long-range coupled protons using the pulse schemes of Fig. 1c and 1d. Since there is no enhancement of carbon signals due to the absence of satura-

Fig. 3. Part of the ^{13}C spectra of 100 mg ml^{-1} cholesteryl acetate in CDCl_3 solvent. The respective pulse schemes used for obtaining the spectra are same as those mentioned for Fig. 2.

tion of protons during relaxation, the scheme of Fig. 1c can also be used for quantitative estimation similar to the scheme 1b. The scheme 1d becomes advantages over 1c for sensitivity reasons since, due to the presence of saturation of protons during relaxation, the intensity of the carbon signals is enhanced by the NOE (spectra g).

The sequences reported herein do not critically depend on the parameters such as delay τ and the pulse widths. Thus, the schemes presented herein have definite advantages in the routine applications for spectral editing and provide a flexibility in picking up an appropriate scheme depending upon the desired information.

Conclusions :

The spectral editing methods presented here for quaternary carbon detection are basically one-dimensional sequences with fewer number of RF pulses. It is noticed from the results of the proposed sequences that the quality of suppression of protonated carbons is extremely good. These, along with the tolerance of the pulse schemes to variations in the delay τ and the pulse widths appear to be important for routine applications. They also promise to play

Fig. 4. Part of the ^{13}C spectra of 40 mg ml^{-1} friedelan-7-one in CDCl_3 solvent. The respective pulse schemes used for obtaining the spectra are same as those mentioned for Fig. 2. A dispersive signal around 41 ppm observed in (g) is an instrumental artifact.

important role for the applications to systems with T_2 limiting cases as well as for systems with low concentration.

Experimental

Experiments using the new pulse schemes are demonstrated on a hexapeptide $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C-O-CO-Val-Val-Val-Aib-Val-Aib-OCH}_3]$, where Aib is methyl-alanyl residue, cholesteryl acetate and friedelan-7-one. All the spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 300 spectrometer equipped with z-gradient accessory at 298 K. The spectra were obtained on a 5 mm QNP probe with a spectral width of 15000, 32 K data points. The spectra were recorded with the number of scans varying from 16 to 200 for different samples and pulse schemes.

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References

1. D. W. Brown, T. T. Nakashima and D. L. Rabenstein, *J. Magn Reson.*, 1981, 45, 302.

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2. C. Le Cocq and J. Y. Lallemand, *J. Chem. Commun.*, 1981, 150.
3. S. Patt and J. N. Shoolery, *J. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, **46**, 535.
4. J. C. Madsen, H. Bildsoe, H. Jakobsen and O. W. Sorensen, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1986, **67**, 243.
5. A. M. Torres, T. T. Nakashima and R. E. D. McClung, *J. Magn. Reson., Ser. A*, 1993, **101**, 285.
6. J. Homer and M. C. Perry, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 373.
7. J. Homer and M. C. Perry, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1995, 533.
8. G. A. Morris and R. Freeman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 760.
9. D. P. Burum and R. R. Ernst, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1980, **39**, 163.
10. O. W. Sorensen and R. R. Ernst, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1983, **51**, 477.
11. M. R. Bendall, D. M. Doddrell and D. T. Pegg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 4603.
12. D. M. Doddrell, D. T. Pegg and M. R. Bendall, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1982, **48**, 323.
13. K. V. Schenker and W. V. Philipsborn, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1986, **66**, 219.
14. H. Bildose, S. Donstrup, H. J. Jakobsen and O. W. Sorensen, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1983, **53**, 154.
15. O. W. Sorensen, S. Donstrup, H. Bildose and H. J. Jakobsen, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1983, **55**, 347.
16. A. E. Derome, "Modern NMR Techniques for Chemistry Research, Organic Chemistry", ed. J. E. Baldwin, Pergamon, Oxford, 1987, Vol. 6, p. 259.
17. G. A. Nagana Gowda, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 2001, **39**, 581.
18. O. W. Sorensen, G. W. Eich, M. H. Levitt, G. Bodenhausen and R. R. Ernst, *Prog. NMR Spectrosc.*, 1983, **16**, 163.

